

SOCIOECONOMIC FACTORS IMPACT ENTERIC PARASITE PREVALENCE AMONG WOMEN IN RAIPUR CITY

¹Dr. A.Rajshekhar, ²Aditaya Sisodiya, ³Aman Ukey, ⁴Muskan Raj Gupta, ⁵Narsing Besra

¹Professor & HoD Geography

^{2,3,4,5}Students VI Sem BAGEN Kalinga University, Raipur

ABSTRACT

For economic development, the majority of developing countries depend on a variety of resources and infrastructure constraints. Nutritional deficiencies, poor environmental conditions, and insufficient educational facilities all have an effect on Females ability to learn. All of these factors would have a significant impact on labor and economic growth, so better resource allocation in nutrition, health care, and education is needed.

Soil-transmitted helminthes parasites infected 1 billion people around the world. This infection is most common in Females in developing countries. This form of infection is largely managed by improved sanitation and living conditions, as well as the availability of anti-helminthic drugs. This has helped to reduce the worm burden and morbidity associated with it. Prosperity, poor and unsanitary living conditions, lack of adequate sanitation and water supply, high humidity, temperature, and soil quality, lack of personal hygiene, use of human fertilizer, and poor health knowledge and literacy for soil-transmitted helminth transmission. Females in various parts of the world are susceptible to soil-transmitted helminthiasis, but there are regional differences. Even though the incidence is lower in the same states of India, the number of children affected is high.

The following points about diseases transmitted by polluted food and water should be emphasized in health education.

- Before eating raw or cooked food, thoroughly wash it with water. Don't eat raw produce straight from the field.
- Before cooking or consuming food, as well as after defecation, wash your hands.
- Drink water from a deep tube well or other healthy source. If water is drawn from a dug well, it should be chlorinated on a regular basis.
- Keep drinking water in clean, covered containers with a narrow mouth. Remove the water with a ladle if you're using a big mouth container. Hands should never be placed inside the jar.
- Safely disposing of human waste, such as by building sanitary latrines to prevent defecation in open fields
- All children and adults should be encouraged to wear shoes instead of going barefoot.
- human feces as fertilizer.

Key Words: Soil-transmitted , infrastructure ,fertilizer, polluted sanitary

INTRODUCTION

A wise saying goes, "Health is Wealth," and everyone in the world wishes to be safe all of the time. However, it is uncommon for a person to go through life without contracting any disease, especially infectious diseases. The human being, the most powerful species on the planet, is parasitized by at least 130 organisms that not only take food and shelter from him, but also cause various diseases. The burden of disease caused by soil transmitted helminths (STH) is enormous among all infectious species. More than 2,000 million people are affected globally, with more than 300 million of them suffering from extreme morbidity; 1, 55,000 deaths are registered per year (W.H.O., 2019). The following table summarizes global estimates of prevalence, mortality, and morbidity (W.H.O., 2019)

Sno.	PARASITE	Prevalence Of Infections (Millions)	Morbidity (cases,millions)	Mortality (deaths,thousands)
1.	Ascaris Lumbricoides	1470	370	62
2.	Hookworms	1320	170	67
3.	Trichuris Trichiura	1070	240	12

With the exception of malaria, these viruses account for more than 40% of the global burden of tropical diseases. STH infections are common in tropical and subtropical areas, especially among poor populations. These infections cause a great deal of pain and death, and they also lead to the perpetuation of poverty by impairing children's cognitive ability and development, as well as adults' work capacity and productivity. In terms of disease burden in developing countries' school-aged populations, intestinal helminth infections are the leading cause of both communicable and noncommunicable diseases.

According to WHO (2019), the number of DALYs (disability-adjusted life years) lost and the ranking of the major causes of disease burden in children aged 5 to 14 in developing countries are as follows:

Sno.	DISEASE	RANK	DALYs lost, in millions (%)
1.	Intestinal helminth infections are parasitic infections that affect the intestines	1	16.8 (11.4%)
2.	Clusters in children (Pertussis- poliomyelitis-measles-tetnus)	2	1 1.9 (8.4%)
3.	Infections of the lungs	3	10.5 (7.4%)
4.	Diarrhoeal diseases are a form of diarrhoea	4	8.8 (6.2%)

5.	Tuberculosis is a form of tuberculosis that affect	5	6.9 (4.9%)
6.	Malaria is a parasitic disease that affects	6	6.5 (3.4%)
7.	Any and all triggers		142.0 (100%)

Soil-transmitted helminth infections cause morbidity and death by:

1. Interfering with nutritional status
2. Having an effect on cognitive functions
3. Resulting in surgical intervention as a result of complications
4. Inducing tissue reactions (Notably granuloma)

The helminths are classified into three groups: Nematodes (round worms) and Trematodes (flukes) and Cestodes (flat worms) (Tapeworms). The manner, in which the worms infect humans, whether by ingestion, skin penetration, or insect infection, has little to do with the helminth community. The life cycle of certain helminths, such as *Enterobius* and *Trichuris*, is extremely simple: eggs move out of the gut, embryonate, and then turn into egg-producing worms in the gut when ingested. Similarly, larvae that have encrusted themselves on meat or vegetables pass through the intestines and turn into tapeworms or intestinal flukes. Ingestion of eggs or skin penetration by larvae, followed by movement through the lungs to the final habitat in the lumen or blood vessels of the gut (*Strongyloides*, Hookworms, and Schistosomes) is a more complex mechanism. Finally, helminths that are ingested or injected (by insects) migrate through the tissues to their final habitats: *Trichinella* - Muscles; *Clonorchis*, *Fasciola*, *Bchinococcus* — Liver; *Paragonimus*, *Bchinococcus* - Lungs; *Onchocerca* - Skin; *Wauchereria* - Lymphatics. Outside the body, the most fundamental structures include eggs alone, progressing by skin penetrating larvae, infectious larvae growth in the flesh of other animals or in biting insects, and eventually, generational alternation in which digenetic trematodes undergo sexual reproduction in a definitive host and asexual reproduction in snails. The majority of helminths do not replicate in a particular human host. They've been dubbed guerrillas because they regularly infiltrate host defenses as individuals or small groups, eventually growing into large forces; combat is normally fought through attrition and lasts a long time. *Strongyloides*, whose larvae can become infectious while in the gut, resulting in overwhelming autoinfection, and *Bchinococcus*, the dog tapeworm, with humans as intermediate hosts, in which larval replication occurs in the so-called hydatid cyst, are important exceptions to this case. Most adult worm species' lack of replication in humans has a range of effects, the most important of which is pathogenesis.

Human populations have an uneven distribution of worms, with the majority of people having low worm burdens. In the case of hookworm infection, the connection between disease and high worm burdens is most clearly demonstrated. Each *Ancylostoma* consumes approximately 0.15 ml of blood per day. Blood loss is minimal in patients with low worm burdens, and anemia is rare, but those with 1000 worms or more can lose more than 100 mL of blood per day. Although it has long been believed that patients with low worm loads were immune and those with high

burdens were not, it is possible that the reverse is true, as a small number of worms does not provide enough antigenic stimulation for immunity to develop. Finally, certain helminth infections necessitate the use of extremely toxic medicines to treat them. It may therefore be better not to treat patients with low worm burdens who have no signs or symptoms of disease; those with many worms may be treated with low, non-toxic drug doses to significantly minimize worm burdens rather than with high, toxic drug doses necessary to obtain a "cure." Since this is the path by which helminths enter and leave the human body, the majority of helminths that infect humans lodge in the gastro-intestinal tract. Gastrointestinal helminths are divided into three groups: Nematoda, Cestodea, and Trematoda. Only Nematode and Cestode infections are found in the Kashmir valley. The following is a brief summary of these two classes:

NEMATODES (ROUND WORMS)

The phylum Nematoda, also known as round worms, is the second largest in the animal world, with over 500,000 species. This phylum's members have elongated bodies and bilaterally symmetric bodies that include an intestinal tract and a large body cavity. Many round worm species exist in the wild, but only a few are parasitic on humans. Intestinal round worm infections, on the other hand, are the most common human helminth infections; for example, it is estimated that there are billion cases of Ascariasis and 800 million cases of trichuriasis worldwide. Since certain parasitic nematode infections can be transmitted directly from infected to uninfected people, the life cycle of parasitic nematodes is important clinically.

Others need eggs to mature outside of the human host, and parasites in a third group may spend part of their life cycle in the soil before being infective to humans. The stage of the parasite's life cycle in the host, as with other parasitic infections, is used to make a definitive diagnosis. Nematodes, like most other human-infectious worms, do not replicate in the host, which is an important biologic and clinical feature because it means that exposure to the infective stage is needed to increase parasite load in an infected person. Strongyloidosis in immunocompromised

people is an exception to this rule, as the parasite can grow into a larval stage within the host without being exposed to worms from the environment.

CESTODES (TAPE WORMS)

In either of the two stages of their life cycle, segmented worms, or tape worms, cause illness: the adult stage, which causes signs and symptoms related to the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, where the adult tape worm resides, and the larval stage, which causes signs and symptoms related to enlarging larval cysts in different tissues of the mammalian host. Because of the impressive length of the adult (up to 30 feet) and the fluid filled cysts in the larval stage that give meat a 'measled' appearance, tape worms have been known since the beginning of documented history. *Taenia saginata*, *Taenia sa Hymenolepis nana*, *Taenia solium*, and *Diphyllobothrium latum* The mammal that helps the cestode to fully grow into an adult segmented worm is the definitive host. Humans are also an acceptable intermediate host for *Taenia solium* and *Hymenolepis nana*. The intermediate host enables the larval stage of the parasite to penetrate the intestinal mucosa and survive in tissue for varying periods of time. Only the larval or intermediate stage of *Echinococcus granulosus* can be supported by humans, and signs of the larval cyst in visceral organs such as the liver and lungs have been observed. The geographical prevalence and distribution of gastrointestinal helminths are heavily influenced by climate, socioeconomic factors, and cultural behaviors. The geography of Jammu and Kashmir makes it a haven for helminths in the gastrointestinal tract. The state is located between 32.15 and 37.05 north latitude and 72.35 and 83.20 east longitude, making it India's northernmost state. The state's total area is 2, 22,236 square kilometers. There are 78,114 square kilometers under Pakistani occupation and 37,555 square kilometers under Chinese occupation. From west to east, the state is bordered by Pakistan, Afghanistan, and China. Among India's states and union territories, the state ranks 6th in terms of area and 17th in terms of population (Gupta, 2006).

People in most areas are forced to defecate in open fields due to a shortage of civil facilities. The vegetables grown in these fields are polluted with human feces, and eating them can lead to helminth infestations. Because they are; school-aged children are an important high-risk category for gastrointestinal helminths.

1. During a time of accelerated physical growth and metabolism, which results in increased nutritional requirements, children are more vulnerable to infection if these needs are not met.
2. Helminth infections have been shown to have a detrimental effect on cognitive tasks during times of intensive learning.
3. Continuously exposed to polluted soil and water, but possibly ignorant of the value of maintaining good personal hygiene.

Given the importance of children's health, a thorough examination of all aspects of helminth parasitization is required. Unfortunately, no comprehensive field study of the incidence of intestinal helminth infection in children and its other implications has been performed in the Kashmir valley, and the current study will be a step in the right direction to fill that void. Increasing public knowledge of the issue, as well as easier availability and increased usage of parasite-fighting chemotherapeutic agents, cannot diminish the public health significance of these parasitic gastrointestinal parasites.

- Sanitation, hygiene, and access to clean water - aimed at limiting transmission by minimizing soil and/or water pollution - are three methods widely considered when preparing control programs for gastrointestinal helminth infestations.
- Education and enhanced housing standards - aimed at minimizing transmission and re-infection by promoting healthier habits.

- Chemotherapy - a treatment aimed at minimizing morbidity by lowering the worm load. This would have an immediate positive impact on children's health and development.

Although sanitation, hygiene, access to safe water, education, and improved housing standards have long-term implications and require constant commitment and substantial financial support to implement parasitic infestation control, issues such as chemotherapy provide short-term control once the burden of parasitism is established in a high-risk group such as children. With this in mind, the current research was undertaken, and the prevalence of gastrointestinal helminth infections in children was investigated. Furthermore, the effects of helminth infections on children's haemoglobin levels, plasma proteins, and nutritional status was studied.

URBAN VERSUS RURAL ENVIRONMENTS

Fundamental variations in the life cycles of these soil-transmitted helminthes may help explain the urban-rural divide between *Ascaris-Trichuris* and hookworm. Ascaroside, an unsaponifiable lipid found within the inner layer of *Ascaris* larvae, is responsible for many of the hardy properties. More than ten years after being deposited, viable *Ascaris* eggs have been retrieved from soil samples. Apart from ascaroside, the parasitology's "five f's," fingers, feces, fomites, flies, and food, may have originated with *Ascaris* in mind. Ingestion of *Ascaris* eggs stuck

to vegetables is one of the most popular routes of transmission. The density of people in urban slums, on the other hand, should make drug distribution and health education easier. Individuals should also have better access to antihelminthic medications for their families' care.

The soil *Ascaris* eggs thrive in less permeable clay soils and their survival rate increases as the depth of the soil decreases. Clay soils are thought to prevent water from dispersing eggs. Part of this finding may be explained by *Ascaris* eggs' vulnerability to direct sunlight. Hookworm eggs, unlike *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* eggs, hatch in the soil and develop first-stage larvae, which only molt to infective larval stages under particular conditions. Temperature (optimal production at 20-30 C), as well as sufficient shade and moisture, all play a role in egg development in the soil. *A. duodenale* eggs hatch slightly faster than *N. americanus* eggs, according to mathematical models based on laboratory results. Hookworm egg hatching, larval growth, and larval migration are all aided by well-aerated, non-adhesive sandy soils (0.5 mm to 2 mm). The presence of silt, which includes small and scarcely visible particles, further enhances the situation. Sandy loam is a term used to describe this type of soil.

Ascaris and *Trichuris* eggs are tougher than hookworm L3 eggs, allowing them to live in drier climates. In arid climates, however, infection rates for *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* are poor. Human *Ascaris* ova do not embryonize at low humidity (less than 80% atmospheric saturation); there appears to be no upper lethal limit on relative humidity. This is most likely the reason for the low infection rates in Chad and Mali, where tropical conditions combined with poverty will normally lead to high endemicity. Moisture is particularly essential for hookworm. Infectious third-stage larvae (L3) move along moisture films. As a result of the presence of moisture, L3 will be able to move vertically in the soil, particularly at night. Since the presence of vegetation helps to avoid evaporation and preserve soil moisture, L3 will migrate to a height of 30-40 cm in 24-48 hours if the moisture film extends this far. Dessication is a problem for L3, and they can move up and down vertically in response to changing moisture conditions before their lipid reserves are depleted. It has been suggested that total rainfall in a region, as well as its seasonal distribution, may help explain observed infection patterns: wetter areas are typically associated with increased transmission of all three major soil transmitted helminthes infections. An analysis of *A. lumbricoides* prevalence to see how it coincides with annual data variables including rainfall and temperature recent research in Uganda, however, shows that moderate to high prevalences can occur. This discrepancy demonstrates how relationships between infection prevalence and environmental variables can be local, so it'll be important to look into them in different ecological zones.

The related variations in temperature and humidity are likely to influence soil helminthes transmission. According to survey results in South Africa, *Ascaris* was found at altitudes up to about 1700m in the Drakensberg Mountains' foothills, though at decreasing prevalence. At altitudes above 2500 m in Ethiopia, prevalence rates of about 30% ascariasis have been recorded. At altitudes of 3800 – 4200 meters in the north Bolivian Altiplano, prevalence rates of 11–15

percent have been recorded. Accessible experimental evidence also supports thermal limits: the optimum temperature for *Ascaris* spp. embryonation has been stated to be 31°C (Seamster, 1950), and 38°C is lethal.

According to these studies and the current results, *A. lumbricoides* has a maximum thermal limit of 40°C. The lower thermal limit may be about 15 degrees Celsius.

Infection with *N. americanus* occurs almost wherever rural poverty and poor sanitation meet tropical climates, as well as in some areas of the subtropics.

SEASON

Soil-transmitted helminth infections have a distinct seasonality in some endemic areas. The phenomenon of arrested growth in hookworm explains why a pre-monsoon increase in fecal egg counts is occasionally observed in West Bengal and other areas. Hookworm transmission rates are higher during the rainy season in some areas where there are distinct rainy and dry seasons. Seasonal pneumonitis caused by *Ascaris* migrations occurs annually in Saudi Arabia from March to May. Seasonal variations in *Ascaris* infection have been related to the application of night soil to crops in Japan.

GENETIC RISK FACTORS

In the case of STH, over dispersion is a typical feature of population distribution patterns. Some researchers believe that certain human populations are more genetically susceptible than others. Despite frequent exposures to the parasite and even anthelmintic chemotherapy, epidemiologic studies in West Bengal have identified a population of people who are predisposed to acquiring severe hookworm infections. *Trichuris* and *Ascaris* infections have also been linked to a predisposition. Immunologic, genetic, or even a combination immunogenetic basis can underpin predisposition to all three soil-transmitted helminthes. In Papua New Guinea, for example, some populations with low worm burdens have been found to be relatively immune to reinfection. Individuals with these characteristics have been observed to mount parasite-specific IgE and eosinophilic responses. In one case, researchers discovered a connection between hookworm-specific IgM responses and lower prevalence and strength. In Bangladesh, however, neither association could be found for *Ascaris* infections. Immunoglobulin levels tend to be closely linked to worm burdens in some cases. This is particularly true of host antibody responses to IgG4.

ETHNICITY AND CULTURE

An apparent association between prevalence, worm burden, and ethnicity has been identified in a few well-documented cases. This includes higher *Ascaris* infection rates among more sedentary Bantus in the Central African Republic compared to Pygmies, as well as higher infection rates in Malay or Indian people in Malaysia compared to Chinese. In India, researchers discovered a higher prevalence of hookworm among Muslims than among Hindus, despite the fact that both groups live in close proximity to one another and their actions in terms of risk factors normally associated with soil-transmitted helminth infections did not differ significantly.

HOUSING AND FAMILY

Children from large families have been shown to have higher *Ascaris* prevalence and worm burdens. In a large family, the order in which a child is born may have an effect on his chances of being infected. Houses made of wood and bamboo in Panama is associated with substantially higher rates of soil-transmitted helminth infections than concrete houses.

FOOD

While *Ascaris* eggs and hookworm larvae are not traditionally considered food-borne illnesses, they will stick to vegetables and, if not properly composed for sewage treatment, will be readily distributed in food markets. According to a Japanese study, *Ascaris* eggs were found on 1178 of 2750 objects at one time. Vegetables are available in 40 Tokyo stores. When compared to a group of children who did not live in an area of Marrakesh, Morocco where raw sewage is used for agricultural irrigation, children living in that area had significantly higher prevalence of *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* infections.

Poverty, unsafe and unsanitary living conditions, lack of adequate sanitation and water supply, high humidity, temperature, and soil quality, lack of personal hygiene, use of human fertilizer, and poor health knowledge and literacy are all risk factors for soil-transmitted helminthes transmission. Children in various parts of the world are susceptible to soil-transmitted helminthiasis, but there are regional differences. Even though the incidence is lower in the same states of India, the number of children affected is high.

There is a great deal of malnutrition, and part of it can be due to helminth infection spread through the soil. The effect of soil-transmitted helminthes on children's health is due to anemia in children. In India and other parts of the world where it is common, the impact on children's growth appears to be linked to soil-transmitted helminthes infections. It's difficult to find specific information to describe the relationship between one worm infestation and its effect on health because it's difficult to figure out.

In slums and rural areas, there is a scarcity of clean and portable drinking water. People who live in these areas eat and drink with utensils. As a result, children aged 4 to 15 are more susceptible to infection with a soil-transmitted helminth, especially in slums and rural areas where an adequate supply of walk borefooted is unavailable. The prevalence of soil transmitted helmint infection is high in these regions, according to the studies.

Ascaris, *trichuris*, and hookworms (*Nectoramericanus* and *Ancylostomaduodenale*) are transmitted through the eal-oral route for *ascaris*, *trichuris*, and skin penetration for hookworms (*Nectoramericanus* and *Ancylostomaduodenale*), school children are the most affected due to bad habits, poor personal hygiene, and playing in infected environments, particularly borefooted, which is common in India. As a result, soil-transmitted helminth infections are a major problem that causes further harm by stunting children's mental and physical development, robbing them of a healthy life throughout their lives. The severity of the problem is compounded by the prevalence of disease-friendly conditions in India.

However, we do see that integrating ral effects in a holistic manner in health improvement will help to achieve the goal of reducing the burden of soil-transmitted helminthes among children. The phenomenon of arrested growth in hookworm explains why a pre-monsoon increase in fecal egg counts is sometimes observed in West Bengal and bothers areas. Hookworm transmission rates are higher during the rainy season in some areas where there are distinct rainy and dry seasons. Seasonal pneumonitis caused by *Ascaris* migrations occurs annually in Saudi Arabia from March to May. Seasonal variations in *Ascaris* infection have been related to the application of night soil to crops in Japan.

It's been proposed that total rainfall and its seasonal distribution in a given region can help explain observed infection patterns: Increased transmission of all three major soil transmitted helminth infections is typically associated with wetter areas. An analysis of *A. lumbricoides* prevalence to see how it coincides with annual data variables including rainfall and temperature recent research in Uganda, however, shows that moderate to high prevalences can occur. This discrepancy demonstrates how relationships between infection prevalence and environmental variables can be local, so it'll be important to look into them in different ecological zones. The related variations in temperature and humidity are likely to impact soil helminth transmission. According to survey findings in South Africa, *Ascaris* was present at altitudes up to about 1700m in the Drakensberg Mountains' foothills, though at a decreasing prevalence. At altitudes above 2500 m in Ethiopia, prevalence rates of about 30% ascariasis have been recorded. At altitudes of 3800 – 4200 meters in the north Bolivian Altiplano, prevalence rates of 11–15 percent have been recorded. One component of a comprehensive helminth infection control strategy should be the elimination of severe poverty and hunger.

The positive effects of dewarming have been shown to have a positive impact on professional income in later years. When infected with a soil-transmitted helminthes virus, children are more likely to become malnourished. According to studies conducted in India, the effects of dewarming are extremely beneficial. Dewarmed children gained 35 percent more weight after being dewarmed twice in a year within two years.

- **Achieve universal primary education:** Dewarming will reduce absenteeism by 25% in developing countries, resulting in higher salaries. Soil-transmitted helminthes infection is estimated to cause 16 million cases of mentas retardation in primary school children and 200 million years of primary school failure in developing countries, according to reports.
- **Promote gender equality and empower women:** According to India's great leader, Mr. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, "if you educate a child, you educate only a boy; if you educate a girl, you educate the entire family." Outside of the agricultural sector, there are opportunities for jobs. While the gender gap is closing in developed countries, girls still make up a smaller percentage of students in school than boys. When paired with other measures such as midday meals and take-home rations, dewarming programs have shown to increase the number of girls enrolled. According to a study conducted by Khanal p et al. in Nepal in 2000, offering a midday meal and

food gifts for girls to take home resulted in a 43 percent rise in school enrolment among girls, as well as an improvement in anemia.

- Lower infant mortality and improve maternal health: A soil-transmitted helminth parasite puts children at risk of infection diseases. According to studies performed in areas where malaria is a major killer disease, deworming and the subsequent improvement in survival rates in serious malaria cases.
- Encouraging good hygiene and sanitation practices: Through community capacity building programs and school curriculum, focus should be put on the use of latrines, proper hand washing, and proper foot wear for school children and caregiver's facilities for sanitation all schools should be required to provide a clean water source and sanitation facilities.
- Deworming services: The Ministry of Health should provide deworming programs in school health screenings on a regular basis. Intestinal parasite control systems must concentrate on the highly infected person who is epidemiologically relevant, since they are the primary sources of infection in the population. The mass treatment of heavily infected people will rapidly get hookworm diseases under control. Morbidity can be minimized by changing environmental conditions with the right inputs. Sanitary latrines, food hygiene, safe drinking water, anti-helminthic medications, and health education may be needed. However, in the absence of sanitation, re-infection will occur, necessitating periodic re-treatment. As a side advantage, both of these investments will solve other food/water borne diseases.

Better outcomes can be obtained by educating the society, with a particular emphasis on vulnerable groups of the population (children and mothers), on how to follow the lines together with the recommended chemotherapeutic intervention. Parents and teachers will assist children by instilling healthy habits that will protect them from intestinal infections and other diseases spread by infected food and water. In health education, the following points should be stressed.

- Before eating raw or cooked food, thoroughly wash it with water. Don't eat raw produce straight from the field.
- Before cooking or consuming food, as well as after defecation, wash your hands.
- Drink water from a deep tube well or other healthy source. If water is drawn from a dug well, it should be chlorinated on a regular basis.
- Keep drinking water in clean, covered containers with a narrow mouth. Remove the water with a ladle if you're using a big mouth container. Hands should never be placed inside the jar.
- Safely disposing of human waste, such as by building sanitary latrines to prevent defecation in open fields
- All children and adults should be encouraged to wear shoes instead of going barefoot.
- The use of human feces as fertilizer

Fundamental variations in the life cycles of these soil-transmitted helminths may help explain the urban-rural divide between *Ascaris-Trichuris* and hookworm. Ascaroside, an unsaponifiable lipid found within the inner layer of *Ascaris* larvae, is responsible for many of the

hardy properties. More than ten years after being deposited, viable *Ascaris* eggs have been retrieved from soil samples. Apart from ascaroside, the parasitology's "five f's," fingers, feces, fomites, flies, and food, may have originated with *Ascaris* in mind. Ingestion of *Ascaris* eggs stuck to vegetables is one of the most popular routes of transmission. The density of people in urban slums, on the other hand, should make drug distribution and health education easier. Individuals should also have better access to antihelmintic medications for their families' care. The soil *Ascaris* eggs thrive in less permeable clay soils and their survival rate increases as the depth of the soil decreases. Clay soils are thought to prevent water from dispersing eggs. Part of this finding may be explained by *Ascaris* eggs' vulnerability to direct sunlight. Hookworm eggs, unlike *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* eggs, hatch in the soil and develop first-stage larvae, which only molt to infective larval stages under particular conditions. Temperature (optimal production at 20- 30 C), as well as sufficient shade and moisture, all play a role in egg development in the soil

A. duodenale eggs hatch slightly faster than *N. americanus* eggs, according to mathematical models based on laboratory results. Hookworm egg hatching, larval growth, and larval migration are all aided by well-aerated, non-adhesive sandy soils (0.5 mm to 2 mm). The presence of silt, which includes small and scarcely visible particles, further enhances the situation. Sandy loam is a term used to describe this type of soil. *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* eggs are tougher than hookworm L3 eggs, allowing them to live in drier climates. In arid climates, however, infection rates for *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* are poor. Human *Ascaris* ova do not embryonize at low humidity (atmospheric saturation less than 80%); there appears to be no upper lethal limit on relative humidity. This is most likely the reason for the low infection rates in Chad and Mali, where tropical conditions combined with poverty will normally lead to high endemicity. Moisture is particularly essential for hookworm. Infectious third-stage larvae (L3) move along moisture films. As a result of the presence of moisture, L3 will be able to move vertically in the soil, particularly at night. Since vegetation helps to avoid evaporation and preserve soil moisture, it's a good idea to have some around. If the moisture film spreads this far around vegetation, L3 can migrate to a height of 30-40 cm in 24-48 hours. Desiccation is a concern for L3, and they can move up and down vertically in response to changing moisture conditions before their lipid reserves are depleted. Wetter areas are normally associated with increased transmission of all three major soil transmitted helminth infections. It has been proposed that total rainfall in a region and its seasonal distribution can also help explain observed infection trends. An analysis of the prevalence of *A. lumbricoides* in relation to annual data variables such as rainfall and temperature recent research in Uganda, however, shows that moderate to high prevalences can occur. This discrepancy demonstrates how relationships between infection prevalence and environmental variables can be local, so it'll be important to look into them in different ecological zones.

The related variations in temperature and humidity are likely to impact soil helminth transmission. According to survey findings in South Africa, *Ascaris* was present at altitudes up to about 1700m in the Drakensberg Mountains' foothills, though at a decreasing prevalence. At

altitudes above 2500 m in Ethiopia, prevalence rates of about 30% ascariasis have been recorded. At altitudes of 3800 – 4200 meters in the north Bolivian Altiplano, prevalence rates of 11–15 percent have been recorded.

Soil-transmitted helminth infections have a distinct seasonal pattern. The phenomenon of arrested growth in hookworm explains why a pre-monsoon increase in fecal egg counts is occasionally observed in West Bengal and other areas. Hookworm transmission rates are higher during the rainy season in some areas where there are distinct rainy and dry seasons. Seasonal pneumonitis caused by *Ascaris* migrations occurs annually in Saudi Arabia from March to May. Seasonal variations in *Ascaris* infection have been related to the application of night soil to crops in Japan. In the case of STH, over dispersion is a typical feature of population distribution patterns. Some researchers believe that certain human populations are more genetically susceptible than others. Despite frequent exposures to the parasite and even anthelmintic chemotherapy, epidemiologic studies in West Bengal have identified a population of people who are predisposed to acquiring severe hookworm infections. *Trichuris* and *Ascaris* infections have also been linked to a predisposition. Immunologic, genetic, or even a combination immunogenetic basis can underpin predisposition to all three soil-transmitted helminthes. In Papua New Guinea, for example, some populations with low worm burdens have been found to be relatively immune to reinfection. Individuals with these characteristics have been observed to mount parasite-specific IgE and eosinophilic responses. In one case, researchers discovered a connection between hookworm-specific IgM responses and lower prevalence and strength. In Bangladesh, however, neither association could be found for *Ascaris* infections. Immunoglobulin levels tend to be closely linked to worm burdens in some cases. This is particularly true of host antibody responses to IgG4. For economic development, the majority of developing countries depend on a variety of resources and infrastructure constraints. Nutritional deficiencies, poor environmental conditions, and insufficient educational facilities all have an effect on children's ability to learn. All of these factors would have a significant impact on labor and economic growth, so better resource allocation in nutrition, health care, and education is needed. Soil-transmitted helminthes parasites infected 1 billion people around the world. This infection is most common in children in developing countries. This form of infection is largely managed by improved sanitation and living conditions, as well as the availability of anti-helminthic drugs. This has helped to reduce the worm burden and morbidity associated with it.

The survey is recommended by the World Health Organization. The activity is undeniably carried out among schoolchildren. To control the infection, anthelmintic drugs are provided based on the results of the survey. For high prevalence and severity, this method is also extended to the whole population. When there is a high prevalence and severity, care is given. Much of this happened in a low-income neighborhood. About 70% of school-aged children are malnourished. In the total population of the planet, 30% is anemic. Anemia and malnutrition caused by soil-transmitted helminthes infection are closely linked to iron deficiency, anemia and

malnutrition, vitamin and foliate deficiency, anemia and malnutrition can cause death in school children and in pregnant women, anemia and malnutrition can cause inappropriate growth and development of infected people.

Round worms like *Ascaris lumbricoides*, whip worms like *Trichuris trichiura*, and anthropophilic hookworms like *Nectar americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenales* are the most common soil-transmitted helminthes parasites. The adult stage of the soil transmitted helminthes parasite affects the gastrointestinal tracts, reproduces sexually, and produces eggs that are released into the atmosphere via the faeces.

Hookworm may trigger blood loss in the intestine, resulting in iron deficiency and protein malnutrition. Many of these helminths that are spread by infected soil have an effect on humans. There is a great deal of malnutrition, and part of it can be due to helminth infection spread through the soil. Anemia among infants, as well as the effect on ill growth of children in India and other parts of the world where it is prevalent, tend to be linked to soil transmitted helminth infections. It's difficult to find specific information to describe the relationship between one worm infestation and its effect on health because it's difficult to figure out. In slums and rural areas, there is a scarcity of clean and portable drinking water. People who live in these areas eat and drink with utensils. As a result, children aged 4 to 15 are more susceptible to infection with a soil-transmitted helminth, especially in slums and rural areas where an adequate supply of walk barefooted is unavailable. The prevalence of soil transmitted helminth infection is high in these regions, according to the studies.

Ascaris, *trichuris*, and hookworms (*nector americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenale*) are transmitted through the oral-oral route for *ascaris*, *trichuris*, and skin penetration for hookworms (*nector americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenale*), school children are the most affected due to bad habits, poor personal hygiene, and playing in infected environments, particularly barefooted, which is common in India. As a result, soil-transmitted helminth infections are a major problem that causes further harm by stunting children's mental and physical development, robbing them of a healthy life throughout their lives. The severity of the problem is compounded by the prevalence of disease-friendly conditions in India.

However, we do see that combining will help to achieve the aim of reducing soil-transmitted helminthes burden among children if real impact is rendered in a comprehensive manner in health improvement.

The phenomenon of arrested growth in hookworm explains why a pre-monsoon increase in fecal egg counts is sometimes observed in West Bengal and others areas. Hookworm transmission rates are higher during the rainy season in some areas where there are distinct rainy and dry seasons. Seasonal pneumonitis caused by *Ascaris* migrations occurs annually in Saudi Arabia from March to May. Seasonal variations in *Ascaris* infection have been related to the application of nightsoil to crops in Japan.

It's been proposed that overall rainfall and its seasonal distribution in a given region can help explain observed infection patterns: wetter areas are typically associated with increased transmission of all three major soil transmitted helminth infections. An analysis of *A. lumbricoides* prevalence to see how it coincides with annual data variables including rainfall and temperature recent research in Uganda, however, shows that moderate to high prevalences can occur. This discrepancy demonstrates how relationships between infection prevalence and environmental variables can be local, so it'll be important to look into them in different ecological zones.

The related variations in temperature and humidity are likely to impact soil helminth transmission. According to survey findings in South Africa, *Ascaris* was present at altitudes up to about 1700m in the Drakensberg Mountains' foothills, though at a decreasing prevalence. At altitudes above 2500 m in Ethiopia, prevalence rates of about 30% ascariasis have been recorded. At altitudes of 3800 – 4200 meters in the north Bolivian Altiplano, prevalence rates of 11–15 percent have been recorded. The optimum temperature for the embryonation of *Ascaris* spp. has been stated to be 31o C, and 38o C is lethal, according to available experimental evidence.

According to these studies and the current results, *A. lumbricoides* has a maximum thermal limit of 40o C. The lower thermal limit may be about 15 degrees Celsius.

Infection with *N. americanus* occurs almost wherever rural poverty and poor sanitation meet tropical climates, as well as in some areas of the subtropics.

Fundamental variations in the life cycles of these soil-transmitted helminths may help explain the urban-rural divide between *Ascaris-Trichuris* and hookworm. Ascaroside, an unsaponifiable lipid found within the inner layer of *Ascaris* larvae, is responsible for many of the hardy properties. More than ten years after being deposited, viable *Ascaris* eggs have been retrieved from soil samples. Apart from ascaroside, the parasitology's "five f's," fingers, feces, fomites, flies, and food, may have originated with *Ascaris* in mind. Ingestion of *Ascaris* eggs stuck to vegetables is one of the most popular routes of transmission.

The density of people in urban slums, on the other hand, should make drug distribution and health education easier. Individuals should also have better access to antihelmintic medications for their families' care.

Soil *Ascaris* eggs grow in clay soils that are less permeable, with survivability increasing as the depth of the soil decreases. Clay soils are thought to prevent water from dispersing eggs. Part of this finding may be explained by *Ascaris* eggs' vulnerability to direct sunlight. Hookworm eggs, unlike *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* eggs, hatch in the soil and develop first-stage larvae, which only molt to infective larval stages under particular conditions. Temperature (optimal production at 20- 30 C), as well as sufficient shade and moisture, all play a role in egg development in the soil

A. duodenale eggs hatch slightly faster than *N. americanus* eggs, according to mathematical models based on laboratory results. Hookworm egg hatching, larval growth, and larval migration are all aided by well-aerated, non-adhesive sandy soils (0.5 mm to 2 mm). The presence of silt, which includes small and scarcely visible particles, further enhances the situation. Sandy loam is

a term used to describe this type of soil. *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* eggs are tougher than hookworm L3 eggs, allowing them to live in drier climates. In arid climates, however, infection rates for *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* are poor. Human *Ascaris* ova do not embryonize at low humidity (less than 80% atmospheric saturation); there appears to be no upper lethal limit on relative humidity. This is most likely the reason for the low infection rates in Chad and Mali, where tropical conditions combined with poverty will normally lead to high endemicity. Moisture is particularly essential for hookworm. Infectious third-stage larvae (L3) move along moisture films. As a result of the presence of moisture, L3 will be able to move vertically in the soil, particularly at night. Since vegetation helps to avoid evaporation and preserve soil moisture, it's a good idea to have some around. If the moisture film spreads this far around vegetation, L3 can migrate to a height of 30-40 cm in 24-48 hours. Dessication is a problem for L3, and they can move up and down vertically in response to changing moisture conditions before their lipid reserves are depleted.

It's been proposed that overall rainfall and its seasonal distribution in a given region can help explain observed infection patterns: wetter areas are typically associated with increased transmission of all three major soil transmitted helminth infections. An analysis of *A. lumbricoides* prevalence to see how it coincides with annual data variables including rainfall and temperature recent research in Uganda, however, shows that moderate to high prevalence can occur. This discrepancy demonstrates how relationships between infection prevalence and environmental variables can be local, so it'll be important to look into them in different ecological zones.

SCOPE OF WORK

The survey is recommended by the World Health Organization. To control the infection, antihelminthic drugs are provided based on the results of the survey. For high prevalence and severity, this method is also extended to the whole population. When there is a high prevalence and severity, care is given. Much of this happened in a low-income neighborhood. About 70% of Females Inhabitants are malnourished. In the total population of the planet, 30% is anemic. Anemia and malnutrition caused by soil-transmitted helminthes infection are closely linked to iron deficiency, anemia and malnutrition, vitamin and foliate deficiency, anemia and malnutrition can cause death in pregnant women, and anemia and malnutrition can cause inappropriate growth and development of infected people.

There is a great deal of malnutrition, and part of it can be due to helminth infection spread through the soil. The effect of helminths transmitted through the soil on Female health is due to anemia. In India and other parts of the world where it is common, the impact on Female growth appears to be linked to soil-transmitted helminthes infections. It's difficult to find specific information to describe the relationship between one worm infestation and its effect on health because it's difficult to figure out. Poverty, unsafe and unsanitary living conditions, lack of adequate sanitation and water supply, high humidity, temperature, and soil quality, lack of personal hygiene, use of human fertilizer, and poor health knowledge and literacy are all risk factors for soil-transmitted helminth transmission. Female in various parts of the world are susceptible to soil-

transmitted helminthiasis, but there are regional differences. Even though the incidence is lower in the same states of India, the number of Female affected is high.

In slums and rural areas, there is a scarcity of clean and portable drinking water. People who live in these areas eat and drink with utensils. As a result, Female Inhabitants are more susceptible to infection with soil-transmitted helminths, especially in slums and rural areas where there is a scarcity of walk barefooted. The prevalence of soil transmitted helminth infection is high in these regions, according to the studies. The worms are transmitted through the oral-oral route for *ascaris*, *trichuris*, and skin penetration for hookworms (*ncylostoma americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenale*). As a result of bad habits, poor personal hygiene, and playing in infected environments, particularly barefooted, which is common in India, Female Inhabitants are the most affected. As a result, soil-transmitted helminth infections are a major problem that causes further harm by stunting Female mental and physical development, robbing them of a healthy life throughout their lives. The severity of the problem is compounded by the prevalence of disease-friendly conditions in India.

However, we do see that combining will help to achieve the aim of reducing soil-transmitted helminth burden among Female if real impact is rendered in a comprehensive manner in health improvement.

PROBLEM ON HAND

Soil-transmitted helminth parasites infected 1 billion people around the world. This infection is most common in Females in developing countries. This form of infection is largely managed by improved sanitation and living conditions, as well as the availability of anti-helminthic drugs. This has helped to reduce the worm burden and morbidity associated with it. Much of this happened in a low-income neighborhood. About 70% of Female Inhabitants are malnourished. In the total population of the planet, 30% is anemic. Anemia and malnutrition caused by soil-transmitted helminth infection are closely linked to iron deficiency, anemia and malnutrition, vitamin and foliate deficiency, anemia and malnutrition can cause death in school children and in pregnant women, anemia and malnutrition can cause inappropriate growth and development of infected people.

Our research is being conducted in the Raipur city. These people are uninformed about their health and are afflicted with a variety of diseases, including soil-transmitted helminth. In the years 2019-2020, survey studies were performed in October and November. The rural communities of the Raipur city are unaware of the numerous diseases and other diseases that are rapidly spreading. One of the diseases caused by helminth is soil-transmitted helminth, which also led to infant growth and retardation. Poverty, unsafe and unsanitary living conditions, lack of adequate sanitation and water supply, high humidity, temperature, and soil quality, lack of personal hygiene, use of human fertilizer, and poor health knowledge and literacy are all risk factors for soil-transmitted helminth transmission. Female in various parts of the world are susceptible to soil-

transmitted helminthiasis, but there are regional differences. Even though the incidence is lower in the same states of India, the number of children affected is high.

In slums and rural areas, there is a scarcity of clean and portable drinking water. The worms are transmitted through the oral-oral route for *acaris*, *trichuris*, and skin penetration for hookworms (*nector americanus* and *Ancylostoma duodenale*). As a result of bad habits, poor personal hygiene, and playing in infected environments, particularly barefooted, which is common in India, school children are the most affected.

REFERENCES

- Ahsan UM, Abdul B, Aziz UR, Khawaja FQ (2020), frequency of intestinal parasite contamination in kids medical clinic quetta, pakistan *j.med res*, 44(2), 2020
- Ahmed A, Al-Mekhlafi HM, Al-Adhroey AH, Ithoi I, Abdulsalam A M, Surin J (2020), The healthful effects of soil-sent helminths contaminations among Orang Asli schoolchildren in rustic Malaysia, *Parasites and Vectors* , 5:119
- Belizario Jr VY , Totañes FIG, de Leon WU, Lumampao YF, Ciro RNT(2020), Soil-communicated helminth and other intestinal parasitic diseases among younger students in native individuals networks in Davao del Norte, Philippines, *Acta Tropica*, Volume 120, Supplement 1, September 2011, Pages S12–S18
- Chowdhary AB and Schiller E L (2020), a Survey of Parasitic Infections in a Rural Community close to Calcutta, *American J. of Epidemiology* Vol. 87 (2): 299-312.
- Chandrashekhar TS, Joshi HS, Gurung M, Subba SH, Rana MS and Shivananda PG (2020), Prevalence and dispersion of intestinal parasitic pervasions among younger students in Kaski District, Western Nepal, *Journal of Medicine and Biomedical Research*, Vol. 4, No. 1; 78-82
- Dangana A, Abayomi RO, Way GD and Akobi OA(2019), Survey of *Ascaris lumbricoides* among understudies of elementary school in Jos south nearby government zone of Plateau State, Nigeria, *African Journal of Microbiology Research* Vol. 5(17), pp. 2524-2527